

Emotional Intelligence: Innovative Business Model for Enhancing overall Organization Performance

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Abstract: When we are working in professional organization or environment, most of the time we face some sort of dilemma or challenge that how to handle the particular problem or situation in such a way so that the feeling of other person could not hurt and we generally try to achieve win-win situation whereby through system process the situation could be handled. Hence we could arrive on wise decision. So in this regard Emotional Intelligence is considered as one of the significant tool to deal with such type of challenges (Marc, 2011). The main aim of this study was to investigate the impact of emotional intelligence, an Innovative Business model on enhancing the organizational overall performance. For this purpose, sample of 100 respondents were collected and Structural equation modeling was applied. At the end, it was concluded that Emotional Intelligence dimensions such as Self- Awareness, Self- Management, Relationship Management and Social Awareness was significantly impacted and enhanced the organizational overall performance.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, SEM, Innovative Business Model, win-win Situation

Introduction

The terminology Emotional Intelligence was first proposed by Salovey (1990) in the beginning of 1990's. And thereafter the term was republished by Goleman (1996). They defined the term "As the ability of the individual's to recognize and deal with their own feelings and same ability enables the individual to make them understand and handle the feeling of other individuals in better manner. There were number of models developed by the researchers over aperiod of time, but Goleman (2002) developed a better model to understand the individual self and other feelings. He proposed four Emotional Intelligence dimensions such as Self- Awareness, Self- Management, Relationship Management and Social Awareness. Thereafter number of researcher proposed their dimensions with different vocabulary (Nwokah, 2009).

Self-awareness is related with how well one individual is aware about their own emotions and also aware the effect of their emotions on decision making, behaviours. Similarly the level of confidence he is having and its impact on inner as well as external self (Danguah, 2014).Self-management refers to the individual ability to manage the inner self in best possible manner so that we could interact with other individuals as we should expect the to our-self (Karimi, 2014). Social awareness is related with one individual must be aware the socially defined norms and what is acceptable in the society and we should behave in such a way. An emphatic person can easily handle all the situations. As a part complex and dynamic environment, person should be more vigilant and empathetic towards other person at the time of communication. Relationship management is related with the basics social skills required in the person. We should behave in such a way so that the same behaviour could be expected from other also (Karimi, 2014).

Kahtani (2013) stated that performance is related with outcome of the work and it is particularly achieved by the individual or group of people. Performance is associated with authority and responsibility. And Employee performance means series of activities performed by the employees to achieve the organizational objectives and their performance are measured against the pre-determined targets. For this purpose, authority and responsibility are assigned to them. And their

performance is measure under different parameters such as quality, sincerity, timely, quantitatively etc.

Review of Literature

Salovey (1990) studied the concept "Emotional Intelligence". In this article, firstly they presented the framework on emotional intelligence. They studied accurate appraisal, emotions, feelings etc. finally, at the they concluded that emotional intelligence is must for mental health. Goleman (1996) They defined the term "As the ability of the individual's to recognize and deal with their own feelings and same ability enables the individual to make them understand and handle the feeling of other individuals in better manner. There were number of models developed by the researchers over a period of time. Goleman (2001) discussed that Emotional intelligence is more important than any other assets, any technical expertise and it must be considered as most significant factor for career growth. Goleman (2002) developed a better model to understand the individual self and other feelings. He proposed four Emotional Intelligence dimensions such as Self- Awareness, Self-Management, Relationship Management and Social Awareness.

Jorfi (2010) studied the effect of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance. The main objective of this study was to understand the emotional intelligence level of employees in educational institutes. At the end, it was concluded that the emotional intelligence had the positive impact on the performance of the employees. Gunu (2014) examined the Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Employees' Performance and Organizational Commitment: A Case Study of Dangote Flour Mills Workers. The objective of the study is to examine the impact of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment and employees' performance in the manufacturing industry. A sample of 206 respondents was taken into consideration and at the end it was concluded that emotional intelligence had the positive impact on the performance of the employees and employees commitment level. Dhani (2017) studied the effect of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance of IT employees: A gender study. The main purpose of this study was to establish a relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance. At the end, it was concluded that females were better performers than male. Bandi (2019) studied the effect of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance. The main objective of this study was to review the impact of Emotional Intelligence on Job Performance. At the end, it was concluded that emotional intelligence had the positive

impact on the performance of the employee. Gong (2019) studied the influence of emotional intelligence on job burnout and job performance: Mediating effect of psychological capital. For this purpose, he conducted survey of 450 employees of different companies and came to the conclusion that emotional intelligence has positive effect on job burnout and job performance and psychological capital has negative effect on job burnout and job performance. Liberty (2019) conducted the study on effect of emotional intelligence on job performance. He conducted this study with the help of 130 samples. And for this purpose six companies were taken into consideration. At the end, it was concluded that emotional intelligence has positive effect on job performance as compare to the monetary rewards and finally it was recommended that all the managers should focus on emotional intelligence rather to measure their performance. Shivangi (2020) examined emotional Intelligence and its Impact on Employee Performance and Stress Level While Working from Home. The main purpose of this study was importance of emotional intelligence and impacts on employee performance their stress level. At the end, it was concluded that significant relationship exist between emotional intelligence and employee performance.

Research Objective

- To examine the impact of emotional intelligence on the performance of employees and manager

Research Methodology

An deductive approach has been applied in this investigation. This approach could facilitate a conclusive theory related to the emotional intelligence and their impact on the employee performance level. A quantitative research method has been used for this research. The survey was conducted on the manager and employees. A purposive sampling technique was used in this investigation. The survey was conducted online on 100 workers and employees.

Ethical Considerations: At the time of adopting quantitative approach, generally the primary research was considered as one of the most significant relevant area for the study. The data was primarily collected from the respondents, so at this point of time, little ethical consideration was necessary to be focused on:

- **Designing the data collection process**
- **How to analyse the collected data**

It is necessary to inform all the participants the objectives of the proposed study. Their participation must be based on their willingness and each participant must have a right to reject your request to fill the questionnaire if he/she is not ready. In addition, it was assured to each and every participant that their responses will be treated with strict confidentiality and will not be given to any third person.

Proposed Model for the study

Data Analy

The data was primarily collected from primary sources and various statistical tools were applied to get the desired result. Specifically EFA, CFA was applied to reach the conclusive point.

Table No- 1 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.910
Sig.	0.001

Source: SPSS 23.0

Table No- 2 Factors, Eigen Value and Cumulative Variance

Factors	Eigen Value	% of Variance	Cumulative % of Variance
Self Awareness	6.705	23.986	23.986
Self Management	5.345	18.744	42.73
Relationship Management	5.354	15.064	57.7934
Social Awareness	2.141	12.490	70.284

Source: SPSS 23.0

Thre result indicated that Eigen value and Cumulative Variance of all factors were 70.284 and it was accepted as per the conditions

Table No-3 Construct Inter Reliability

Factors	Reliability
Self Awareness	0.907
Self Management	0.964
Relationship Management	0.890
Social Awareness	0.867

Source: SPSS 23.0

As per the above table 3, it can be concluded that the reliability analysis of Four factors were appropriate for next step (Malhotra, 2009).

Table No- 4 Factor Loading's

1	Self Awareness	SA1	0.89	Accepted
		SA2	0.87	Accepted
		SA3	0.86	Accepted
2	Self Management	SM1	0.86	Accepted
		SM2	0.84	Accepted
		SM3	0.81	Accepted
3		RM1	0.85	Accepted

	Relationship Management	RM2	0.79	Accepted
		RM3	0.78	Accepted
4	Social Awareness	SA1	0.89	Accepted
		SA2	0.78	Accepted
		SA3	0.75	Accepted

Source: SPSS 23.0

As per the (Black & Hair, 2010), only those statements were taken into consideration, where factor loadings were more than 0.50

Conclusion

The proposed research highlighted the paradigm of organization to highlight the importance of Emotional Intelligence. From the review of literature, it is clearly mentioned that the need of EI in today’s dynamic era. To the end, it was really feasible to conduct the proposed study in the light of review of literature, methods and methodologies, data analytical techniques, and ethical rules. The research will also serve the purpose of corporate world to change their approach in light of Emotional Intelligence. Furthermore, At the end, it was concluded that Emotional Intelligence dimensions such as Self- Awareness, Self- Management, Relationship Management and Social Awareness was significantly impacted and enhanced the organizational overall performance.

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